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LIBRARY INNOVATIONS AND TECHNOLOGICAL CHALLENGES IN DIGITAL AGE

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Content

Advisory Board	v
Editorial Board	v
Organising Committee	vi
Message by Minister, Art & Culture	vii
Message by Secretary, Art & Culture	viii
Foreword	ix
Preface	x
Contributors	xi
1 गोंय भौशीक ग्रंथालय अधिनेम, १९९३ मिलिंद म्हामल	1
2 Drone Delivery Services in Library: An Overview Prashant R. Phadte Vinda S. Gadekar Sarita G. Khalap	10
3 Library Marketing using Blogs: An Overview Dr. Carlos M. Fernandes Padmaja Khedekar Manjita Khedekar	21
4 Library of Things (LoT's), Building a Sustainable Community: Scope for Goan Academic and Public Libraries Novelty (Saanvi) Volvaikar e Morjekar	29

5	Technological Impact in Indexing at State Central Library Goa– An Overview Maria Ana Paiva Sneha S. P. Malkarnekar	45
6	Effectiveness of ICT tools and Applications on Academic Performance among Science Teachers in Karnataka: A Survey Dr. M. H. Prakash	52
7	User's Satisfaction Services Provided by Narayan Zantye College of Commerce Library, Bicholim, Goa: An Overview Bala Mandrekar	67
8	Information Seeking Behaviour of Students of St. Xavier College, Mapusa Goa, - A Case Study Dr. Keshav R. Dhuri Diksha D. Naik	75
9	Innovative Public Library Services in Kerala Prasanth, M.P Senthilkumaran, P	86
10	गोवा सार्वजनिक ग्रंथालये अधिनियम, १९९३ मिलिंद म्हामल	97
11	LibraMart - A New Trend in Traditional and Online Library Marketing in Modern Era Dr. Carlos M. Fernandes Prashant R. Phadte Brijesh B. Chanekar	107

12	Library Websites and Knowledge about Content Management Systems: Need of the Hour in Internet Age Varada Vaman Jog	120
13	Impact of Information Technology on Academic Libraries Dr. Maya Carvalho e Rodrigues	131
14	Smart Libraries Internet of Things Dr. Hemkant M. Chaudhari	144
15	Impact of 21 st Century Technologies on Five Laws of Dr. Ranganathan: Modern Interpretation and Infotech Library Services Sonia M. Desai	153
16	Virtual Reference Services and Changing Role of Reference Librarianship in 21 st Century Dr. Carlos M. Fernandes Suchita V. Mulgaonkar	163
17	Vandalism and its Prevention in Academic Libraries Jovita Lobo	175
18	The Role of Library Professionals in Intellectual Property Rights with Specific Reference to Geographical Indications Dr. Carlos Fernandes Anuja S. Naik Banaulikar Sonali Pednekar	186

19	Conceptualising College e-Learning using Moodle to Enhance Innovation Skills Munesh Kumar Milind Gauns	193
20	Implementation of RFID Technology in Library Management. Sarvesh S. Morje	203
21	Role of Library Professionals of North Goa in Effective Promotion of Library Resources Vassudeo M. Naik	214
22	Proposed Model for Integration of Public Libraries and Community Information Centres Meera Bhosle	226

Library of Things (Lot's), Building a Sustainable Community: Scope for Goan Academic and Public Libraries

Novelty (Saanvi) Volvaikar e Morjekar

Abstract

Libraries have been in existence amongst us for a long time. Libraries, specially the public libraries are considered to be the heart and soul of our communities. Libraries till now have been associated only with books and other forms of documentation which is lent to its patrons for referencing and intellectual pursuits. But, what if the present day libraries extend its services in lending unconventional stuff like power drills, electronic gadgets which are expensive and not used on a regular basis by a person. This paper discusses the coming in existence of the Library of Things (LoT) which lend such unconventional material to its users. The paper aims to make aware about the different types of libraries and how the public libraries and academic libraries can make the best of it and build economically and socially strong communities. The paper also aims to highlight the benefits of such a library to the economy and environment as a whole. The paper also aims to understand the scope of LoT's in the Goan public and academic libraries.

Keywords: *Library of Things(LoT), Human Libraries, Tool Libraries, Academic Libraries, Public Libraries, Economy, Sustainable Community.*

Introduction

Libraries have always been associated with lending or sharing of books and other forms of documentation and now in the present scenario, lending of e-resources. But if we look at libraries in a new light, it is just not about books and e-resources any more. A lot of public libraries around the world have extended their services beyond the lending out of conventional stuff. What if a patron is able to issue out small kitchen appliances or camping gear which we may need just may be once in a while or to say is not regularly used. And, Libraries are just great, awesome when it comes to serving its community. The libraries have opened up great opportunities for lending out of unconventional or non-traditional stuff which have given rise to culture of the Library of Things (LoT).

This paper tries to explain the concept of Library of things and how it can be incorporated in the public libraries and the academic libraries as an extended service with reference to the Goan Libraries. The paper aims to explain how the libraries can help in building a sustainable community.

1. Library of Things (LoT)

Library of Things is not exactly a new concept. Library of Things did exist in the form of tool libraries or toy libraries since 1970's, especially in the USA. These were standalone libraries. But in the present world many public libraries and some academic libraries around the world has incorporated this concept of library of unconventional things as a part of their extended services. The concept of the Library of Things is gaining momentum in many countries. It is more prevalent in the USA and UK and yet to gain momentum in Indian libraries.

The concept of the Library of Things arose out of the need to share resources which are not in high demand in terms of daily usage or are used only occasionally and are very

expensive. The concept behind the Library of Things is to create more buoyant communities by reducing human consumption of natural resources and bolstering communal networks. Library of Things fosters a sharing economy.

The Library of Things offer a wide variety of non-traditional items such as camping gear, fishing poles, items required for baking etc. which are normally not used on an everyday basis. The Library of Things also lends out humans who act as books and such a library is called a human library which is also becoming very prevalent.

According to Gene Homicki, co-founder and CEO of myTurn, the most successful Library of Things are the ones that do more than just lend items but they also create a strong sense of community.

2. Scope

The concept of the LoT's can be incorporated in the libraries of Goa. The LoT's in the public libraries can be on an extensive scale and the academic libraries can have specialized LoT's similar to the Special Libraries.

3. Methodology

The websites of some of the LoT's in the Public libraries and Standalone Libraries were visited to get a fair idea as to the benefits of LoT's, the types of collections, the collection policies, the usage etc. Telephonic interviews were done of the three libraries in India, namely, Auroville Library of Things based in Tamil Nadu, Khilonewala Toy Library based in Indore and its franchisee in Porvorim and the Human Library based in Assagao. The AITD Library is also mentioned as the Library of Things in an academic library.

4. Benefits of a Library of Things

A. Save Money / Cost Efficient:

As the popularity of minimal living standards and the KonMari method, people would prefer to avoid buying expensive and space occupying things whose use is infrequent or minimal, even if they can afford it. Hence, one can save money by borrowing items that one uses very infrequently instead of purchasing them, thus curbing unnecessary expenses.

B. Save the Environment:

By reducing the consumption and purchase of infrequently used items and at the same time reducing the number of items sent to the landfill by sharing the items we can help in saving the environment.

C. Generate Employment:

By adding the library of things section to the libraries, a lot for opportunities for employment is generated.

D. Sharing Economy/ Building Communities:

The library of things will help in fostering the values of sharing by donating things which are hardly in use to the library which in turn can be utilized by the library patrons by loaning them out, thus creating strong communities. The Library of Things collections would be helpful to individuals who cannot afford expensive things but may need at a certain point of time.

5. Types of Library of Things and things that can be borrowed

A. Electronics and Technology:

These include electronic gadgets like tablets, kindles, e-readers, laptops, projectors, scanners, cameras, mouse, headphones, mobile hot spots etc.

B. Gardening and seeds:

This collection includes landscaping tools, lawn movers, gardening tools such as rakes etc. and also seeds. Only thing in this collection is that once the seeds are loaned out they cannot be returned. Hence, some libraries have made it a policy that the person who loans out the seeds will have to save and return the seeds from his or her yield to the seed library the following year.

C. Kitchen collection:

This collection includes popcorn machines, ice-cream makers, blenders, cotton candy maker, cake pans etc. Most of the baking tools are very expensive and hence this collection is very helpful for something one might bake once in a while.

D. Musical instruments:

The musical instrument collection may include instruments such as electric guitar, ukulele, electric keyboard, violin etc.

E. Art and Craft:

This collection may include crafting tools such as sewing machines, embroidery kits, knitting and crochet kits, paintings etc.

F. Home Tools:

Thermometers, vacuum cleaners, etc.

G. Sports Gear and Recreation:

This collection can offer its users a wide variety of items like binoculars, bird watching kits, fishing rods and other fishing gear, badminton kits, karaoke machines, party supplies etc.

H. Science Kits:

Telescopes, microscopes robotics kits, coding toys, Arduino, Raspberry Pi etc.

I. Tool Library:

This collection includes home improvement tools, carpentry tools etc.

J. Toy Library:

Puzzles, board games, puppets etc.

K. Human Library:

A human library is designed to build a positive framework for conversations that can challenge stereotypes and prejudices through dialogue (Human Library Organization n.d.). The human library is a place where real people are lent out to the users. The users converse with the human book. The human library is originally a Danish concept. The human books may be of varied titles like autism, ADHD, Naturist, Homeless. This type of library actually is kind of a self-counseling session for the users as well as the human book. This type of library helps in socializing too.

L. Pet Libraries:

Similar to the human libraries, pet libraries loan out pets to

This Library of Things is privately funded by donations. The items can be loaned out for weeks and an overdue of \$1.00/day is charged. This library is governed by the Collection Development Policy for Library of Things and Guidelines for using the items in collection. The collection includes, assistive listening system, colour blind glasses, mobile hotspots, crafting tools, coding tools, board games etc.

- ii. **Brookline Public Library, Massachusetts, USA** (<https://www.brooklinelibrary.org/what-we-have/library-of-things/>):

The Brookline Public Library has three branches and all have a Library of Things. The Library of Things offers items such as board games, cake pans, record players, telescopes, video games, I pads, kill a watt energy meters, osmo kits, mobile hotspots etc.

- iii. **Sacramento Public Library, California, United States** (<https://www.saclibrary.org/Books/Specialty-Checkouts/Library-of-Things/Library-of-Things-Catalog>):

This public library has a Library of Things at its two branches and lends out items such as guitars, electrical kits lawn mowers etc.

- iv. **Hamilton-Wenham Public Library, MA, USA** (<http://hwlibrary.org/library-of-things/>):

This Library of Things lends out items such as binoculars, board games, cd players, cookie cutters, laploom, google virtual reality glasses etc. Some items such as chargers, ipad etc. can be used only in the library premises.

B. Free Standing Library of Things

i. Sharing Depot, Canada (<https://sharingdepot.ca/>)

This Library of Things was started in 2012 by two friends namely Ryan Dymont and Lawrence Alvarez, who were actively involved in causes involving the environment and economy. The library lends items in the following categories: camping, small home appliances, carpentry and woodworking, electrical and soldering, sports, sustainable living, toys and games, gardening tools etc.

**ii. Share, Frome, England
(<https://sharefrome.org/things/>)**

The idea for SHARE was born in early 2015, as a partnership between Frome Town Council, social enterprise Edventure, Sustainable Frome and the Cheese and Grain, the local music and events venue (Share, A Library of Things n.d.). The library lends out stuff in categories such as gardening tools, DIY, arts and crafts, household, kitchen, leisure etc. They have their own newsletter as well.

**iii. Share Shed, Devon, England, UK
(<https://shareshed.org.uk/>)**

Share Shed is a Library of Things inspired by the Share Frome Project. The charity namely, the 'Network of Wellbeing' decided to explore possibilities of such a venture in Devon, UK. The items are shelved under sections namely DIY, events and party, gardening, home maintenance and cleaning etc.

7. Library of Things, Indian Scenario

As mentioned earlier the concept or idea of a Library of Things has been more prevalent in the USA and UK. Mostly the libraries are standalone. But in the last few years the idea of LoT's have gained momentum and the public as well as academic libraries in these countries are adopting this concept.

In India it is yet to gather momentum. There are standalone video libraries, tool libraries in India but they are not properly organized. A search conducted on the World Wide Web, drew some hits for some standalone Library of Things. Telephonic interactions were held with the individuals concerned as to how they came up with the concept etc. The websites were also visited to check the type of collections etc. The details of these LoT's are as follows;

i. Auroville Library of Things, Bommayapalayam, Tamilnadu(<https://www.earthandus.org/auroville-library-of-things-alot/>)

This library is around one and a half years old. The library is still in the growing phase, hence the collection is small. The library only charges a small security deposit of twenty five rupees. The starting up of the Auroville Library of things was initiated by the Earth and Us, a consultancy firm comprising of sustainability consultants, researchers and educators. The firm and the LoT is located in Auroville, an eco-village inspired by the teachings of Sri Aurobindo in South India. The library began with collecting items like toys, kitchenware and tools and plan to expand their collection further. The mission of the library is to bring about the sharing culture and to help create a sustainable environment.

ii. Khilonewala, Porvorim, Goa (Franchisee)
(<http://khilonewala.in/>)

Khilonewala is a standalone toy library, started in 2011 in Indore. It caters to children in the age range of 1-12 years and lends out toys, games and books. It caters to around 17 states and has fifty plus centres across India. Goa has its franchisee started in December 2018.

iii. Human Library, Assagao (<http://humanlibrary.org>)
(<https://www.facebook.com/projectmadmonkmaya/>)

The concept of the human library or the Menneskebiblioteket (Danish) originated in Copenhagen, Denmark. The first human library was formed in 2000 by Ronni Abergel and Dany Abergel in association with their friends as a project for the Roskilde festival. The human library organization is operational in 6 continents and host events and activities in more than 80 countries.

The human library has found usage in various sectors of the civil society. The idea of the human library is to break stereotypes with the message, “Don’t Judge a Book by its Cover”. The libraries around the world organize events for a week or so of the human library, wherein the users can borrow human books and learn about different cultures and life experiences through dialogue thus breaking stereotypes and prejudices. The human libraries are hosted as events annually.

In India there are human libraries that have started in Hyderabad, Mumbai, Bangalore etc. The first such human library event was organized in Goa in November 2018, and initiative by Ms. Moumita Pal in Assagao. There were seven people who were shortlisted from seventy applicants to be the books. The titles of the books varied from “depression” to “My name is Khan and I am not going to Pakistan” and many more titles. The event was organized for a period of 11 days.

**iv. Agnel Institute of Technology and Design (AITD)
Central Library, Library of Things, Assagao:**

The idea of incorporating the concept of Library of Things was put ahead in the Library committee of the Institute which was approved and thus the Library of Things at AITD started in June 2019. The collection is still under development. Some of

the items in the collection include drafters, mobile chargers, calculators, dividers etc. that the engineering students would require as per their curriculum. The items in the collection are donated by ex-students and staff and some items will be procured for which a separate budget is allocated.

8. Suggestions and concerns for incorporating the concept of LoT's in the public and academic libraries of Goa

Incorporating the concept of LoT's in the Public and Academic libraries would indeed prove a great service to the community it serves. The reasoning behind developing the LoT's in the public and academic libraries is to provide access to something that the library users may otherwise not have access to.

The public libraries can have extensive collections as they are the ones who reach out the masses. The public libraries are often the catalysts of change as per the needs of its users. The collections such as "Electronics", "Gardening", "Small Appliances", "Recreation" can be started. The academic libraries can concentrate on developing collections as per the requirements of the student fraternity. For example a medical library can make a collection of stethoscopes, bone boxes, lab coats etc. Apart from the specialized items the academic libraries can make general collection of headphones, chargers, exam boards, audiovisual equipments, iPads etc.

To have a properly functioning LoT in the library, the following points may be taken into consideration;

- Formulate a collection development policy for the different types of collection in the LoT.
- Identify the things that can go into the collection and the type of collections that can be developed.
- Conduct a survey of the needs of the library users.

- Identify sources from where the library can procure the items for the LoT.
- A lending library software for the Library of Things can be procured namely “myTurn” or the items can be technically processed with the library management software of the institute. myTurn is a platform that makes it possible for people to develop their own lending platform.
- A thorough planning is essential for developing the Library of Things as it is a challenge to maintain the Library of Things section in terms of usage, space etc.
- Finances also need to be checked up.

9. Conclusion

The libraries are the never failing springs of water in a desert, always outdoing itself by trying things that the community will benefit from. LoT's is the new social enterprise that allows its patrons to borrow items from its collection, ranging from recreation items to small home appliances which may or may not be expensive.

In one line to describe a Library of Things is, to REDUCE the purchase of expensive and infrequently used items, REUSE the items by donating them to the Library of Things and RECYCLE by lending it to potential users. Borrowing instead of buying will reduce the items sent to the landfill, thus helping in saving the environment or reducing the ecological harm caused by extensive consumerism. Simply put the LoT's can be considered as organizations that aims to replace individual ownership of expensive and difficult to store stuff and has minimal use, thus helping the people cut down on the clutter. LoT's also help generate employment.

The Library of Things also help in building strong

communities where people can develop meaningful friendships and connections and foster a sharing economy.

Thus, as the libraries have always been considered as the centers of learning, a place for the community members to gather and have always strived to provide the best of resources to the community in the form of tools or skills needed for enrichment of lives, Library of Things would best serve the purpose.

As the sharing culture is gaining momentum, studies showed that the collections in the existing Library of Things are becoming more and more pervasive, imaginative and community-specific. Studies have also shown that the demand for Library of Things is increasing. Developing a Library of Things at the public libraries or the academic libraries of Goa presents an opportunity to create more active spaces for learning, doing things and being with other people.

Hence, this idea or concept may be explored by the public and academic libraries in Goa thus adding to the services it provides to the community and help build strong communities.

“Bad libraries build collections, good libraries build services, great libraries build communities” – R. David Lankes

References

1. *Auroville Library of Things, Bommayapalayam, Tamilnadu.* n.d. <https://aurotot.myturn.com/library/> (accessed June 2019).
2. *Brookline Public Library, Massachusetts, USA.* n.d. <https://www.brooklinelibrary.org/what-we-have/library-of-things/> (accessed June 2019).

3. *Cary Memorial Library, Massachusetts, USA*. n.d. <https://www.caryllibrary.org/library-of-things> (accessed June 2019).
4. Dayal, Krishna, interview by Novelty (Saanvi) Volvaikar e Morjekar. *Auroville Library of Things* (December 20, 2018).
5. D'Souza, Flexcia. *A Library in Goa where books talk!* December 5, 2018. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/entertainment/events/goa/a-library-in-go-where-books-talk/articleshow/66997933.cms> (accessed June 2019).
6. *Earth and Us*. n.d. <https://www.earthandus.org/auroville-library-of-things-alot/> (accessed June 2019).
7. *Goodnet Gateway to doing good*. n.d. <https://www.goodnet.org/articles/at-library-things-you-borrow-almost-anything> (accessed June 2019).
8. *Hamilton-Wenham Public Library, MA, USA*. n.d. <http://hwlibrary.org/library-of-things/> (accessed June 2019).
9. Human Library Organization, Denmark. *Meet our human books*. n.d. <http://humanlibrary.org/meet-our-human-books/> (accessed June 25, 2019).
10. Jain, Bharat, interview by Novelty (Saanvi) Volvaikar e Morjekar. *Khilonewala, Indore* (December 20, 2018).
11. *Khilonewala*. n.d. <http://khilonewala.in/> (accessed June 2019).

12. *Library of Things*. n.d. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Library_of_Things (accessed December 18, 2018).
13. *Library of Things software*. n.d. <https://myturn.com> (accessed June 2019).
14. Naik, Neeraj, interview by Novelty (Saanvi) Volvaikar e Morjekar. *Khilonewala, Porvorim, Goa* (June 2019).
15. Pal, Moumita, interview by Novelty (Saanvi) Volvaikar e Morjekar. *Human Library Organization, Assagao, Goa* (June 2019).
16. *Sacramento Public Library, California, United States*. n.d. <https://www.saclibrary.org/Books/Specialty-Checkouts/Library-of-Things/Library-of-Things-Catalog> (accessed June 2019).
17. *Share Shed, Devon, England, UK*. n.d. <https://shareshed.org.uk/> (accessed June 2019).
18. *Share, A Library of Things*. n.d. <https://sharefrome.org/things/> (accessed June 1, 2019).
19. *Share, Frome, England*. n.d. <https://sharefrome.org/things/> (accessed June 2019).
20. *Sharing Depot, Canada*. n.d. <https://sharingdepot.ca/> (accessed June 2019).
21. *The Human Library Organization, Denmark*. n.d. <http://humanlibrary.org> (accessed June 2019).

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